

Dynamic Logic Families for Complementary Gallium Arsenide (CGaAs) Fabrication Processes

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Abstract- Different Complementary Gallium Arsenide (CGaAs) dynamic logic circuits have been designed, simulated and implemented. The circuits include Domino, N-P Domino, and Two-Phase Dynamic FET Logic (TPDL). These circuits are investigated and compared against complementary static logic for speed, power consumption and layout area. TPDL circuits are the fastest (function properly up to 2.38 GHz) and have the lowest power consumption ever reported in this technology ($0.01 \mu\text{W}/\text{MHz}/\text{gate}$). Moreover, TPDL circuits are self latching and well suited for pipelined architectures.

I. INTRODUCTION

Complementary Gallium Arsenide (CGaAs) fabrication technology is an evolution of GaAs E/D MESFET technology, much like the way CMOS is an evolution of NMOS technology. CGaAs has an advantage over CMOS in that it has no substrate contacts and no latchup possibilities, which reduce the layout area and increase the yield of CGaAs circuits [1]. CGaAs is the lowest power digital technology that is practical for the frequency range of 300 MHz to 1 GHz and above. This technology has already achieved $0.1 \mu\text{W}/\text{MHz}/\text{gate}$ at 0.9 V [2]. Complementary digital ICs can operate at speeds over 500 MHz. By sacrificing some power dissipation, a 1 GHz digital signal processor has been made with a speed/power measurement of $0.16 \mu\text{W}/\text{MHz}/\text{gate}$ [2]. The speed-power performance of $1 \mu\text{m}$ CGaAs has been shown to be superior to $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ CMOS or thin film SOI equivalents [2].

Dynamic logic circuits have been designed in CMOS to decrease the power consumption as well as to increase the maximum operating frequency. Another advantage of dynamic circuits is that they are non ratioed logic. Therefore, the transistor sizes can be minimized to reduce the layout area and power dissipation [3, 4]. CGaAs dynamic logic circuits as well as static logic circuits have been designed and implemented in the research described in this paper. The designed dynamic logic circuits include Domino logic, N-P Domino logic, and Two-Phase dynamic FET logic (TPDL) [5].

II. CIRCUIT DESIGN

In CGaAs static logic circuits, the transconductance ratio of N-channel transistors to P-channel transistors has to be properly adjusted to achieve an acceptable noise margin. The design of the static logic circuits is similar to the design of Silicon CMOS circuits implementing the same logic function. The drive capability of this family is quite low because the load capacitance is connected directly to the output drivers. Thus, transistor gate widths of the driver circuit have to be increased to increase the drive capability, which increases the power consumption and the layout area. They dissipate a static power in addition to the dissipated dynamic power. Also, transistor gate widths should be chosen according to DC transfer curves to get the optimal noise margin.

Domino logic circuits consist of a dynamic N-transistor logic block followed by a static inverter. When the input clock signal is logic low (pre-discharge phase), the circuit output will discharge to the logic low level. When the clock switches to logic high (evaluation phase), the N-transistor logic block will evaluate the input signals and perform the specified logic function. The circuit output either stays at a logic low or charges to logic high (according to the input variables) through the output static inverter. Thus, the output will have at most one transition during evaluation, which prevents erroneous output states that can occur in simple dynamic logic schemes. Transistor gate-widths in the dynamic logic block can be chosen for minimal size because they only drive the static inverter.

N-P Domino logic gates are implemented using N-type and P-type transistor blocks because they use both N-channel transistors and P-channel transistors to evaluate a logic expression. N-type transistor block outputs precharge to V_{DD} while P-type transistor block outputs pre-discharge to zero volts during their precharge phases (zipper operation). This logic family requires the clock and its complement for its operation. During the

precharging phase, all transistor gates of the n-logic blocks are turned off through the preceding p-logic blocks. Also, the transistors of the p-logic blocks will be turned off by the preceding n-logic blocks. Unlike Domino logic, N-P Domino logic is a complete logic family because inverted functions can be directly implemented. It is required that all inputs to N-transistor logic blocks be stable (unchanging) during the evaluation phase (clock is high). The electron mobility is about 5 times the hole mobility in GaAs devices. Thus, the use of the P-type transistors in evaluating the logic is a disadvantage for implementing this family in CGaAs.

Two-Phase Dynamic Logic (TPDL) uses only N-channel transistors in the evaluation part of the circuit. The slow P-channel transistors are used only for precharging the output nodes. TPDL logic requires two clock phases (ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 non-overlapped in the logic low level) and their complements for proper operation. The basic topology of the TPDL circuit is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: CGaAs TPDL Basic Circuit Topology

TPDL circuits consist of ϕ_1 logic-blocks and ϕ_2 logic-blocks. Each logic-block is preceded by one pass gate at each input. The output from each logic block can be sampled (read) at the end of its evaluation phase. Output of a ϕ_1 (ϕ_2) block can not be connected to an input of another ϕ_1 (ϕ_2) block or fed back to itself. The ϕ_1 clock phase and its

complement control the operation of ϕ_1 logic blocks, while the ϕ_2 clock phase and its complement control the operation of ϕ_2 logic blocks.

III. RESULTS AND COMPARISON

In this section, a comparison between the performance of the studied CGaAs logic families is performed. Maximum operating frequency, average power consumption and layout area are compared. Four different logic functions are selected for simulation and implementation using static and dynamic logic families. The selected functions are as follows:

$$F_1 = ((\overline{A+B}) + C), \quad F_2 = ((\overline{A \cdot B}) \cdot C)$$

$$F_3 = ((\overline{A+B}) \cdot C), \quad F_4 = ((\overline{A \cdot B}) + C)$$

The transistor model parameters used in this paper were supplied by Motorola and are representative of the devices manufactured by the Motorola CGaAs fabrication processes. However, the circuits are also compatible with the Honeywell CGaAs fabrication process. These parameters were extracted from actual wafer probing data. The circuits presented here have been simulated in HSPICE which has a superior convergence and accurate modeling features. Therefore, the simulation results should not deviate significantly from the actual measured results obtained when circuit fabrication is completed. The simulated circuits have been implemented using CADENCE tools and sent for fabrication.

The function F_1 will be taken as a study case for the comparison purposes and Table 1 summarizes the comparison results. The design of the static logic circuit is quite easy and similar to the design of Silicon CMOS circuits implementing the same logic function. Static logic has the lowest maximum frequency of operation, the highest power consumption and the largest layout area of all the studied logic families.

CGaAs Domino logic is not a complete logic family because inverted functions can not be directly implemented in this family. Also, it is not completely dynamic because a static inverter is required at each gate output. Its design is more complicated than the static circuit design. Also, it requires a clock signal for proper operation. The main disadvantage of Domino logic is that it is not suitable for pipelined system architectures. The

maximum frequency of operation is more than double that of the static circuits. Also, the layout area is about one-third of the static circuit layout area and the power consumption is much less than that of static circuits implementing the same logic function as shown in Table 1.

TABLE1: Performances Comparison of the Studied CGaAs Logic Families

Logic Family	Maximum Frequency [GHz]	Average Power [mW]
Static	0.62	8.69
Domino	1.61	3.54
N-P Domino	0.82	2.487
TPDL	2.38	2.38

CGaAs N-P Domino dynamic logic is a complete logic family and is completely dynamic (has no static inverters). N-P Domino logic maximum frequency of operation is much lower than that of the Domino logic due to the use of slow P-channel transistor in evaluating the logic. Layout area for both Domino and N-P Domino circuits are comparable. Power consumed by N-P Domino logic circuits is lower than that for the Domino circuits due to the reduction in the dynamic power (frequency dependent).

CGaAs TPDL logic has the highest maximum operating frequency, close to double that of Domino and about four times that of static logic. The layout area is comparable to that of Domino and N-P Domino logic and less than half that for static circuits. TPDL circuit power consumption is significantly below that of the static circuit (less than one third). TPDL circuits do not consume any static power except for a small amount of leakage power (which decreases when lowering the supply voltage). Most of the consumed power is dynamic. Because of the use of pass gates in front of each evaluation circuit, TPDL designs are self-latching and are ideal for pipelined systems. TPDL systems can be pipelined to reach the maximum operating frequency without having to add additional storage elements (pipeline registers).

For a fair comparison, the power consumption should be calculated at the same frequency. If this is

done, TPDL power consumption at the static-circuit maximum operating frequency will be much lower than the value listed in Table 1. Moreover, at this low frequency, related to the maximum frequency of TPDL circuits, TPDL circuits would be powered from a lower power supply voltage and would be operated with lower input and output signal transitions, which dramatically reduces the consumed power.

Figure 2: Power consumption of all logic families at Different Frequencies

The power consumption as a function of frequency for all the studied logic families implementing the function F_1 are shown in Figure 2. This figure illustrates the low power consumption of the TPDL design compared to all other designs. Looking at the above comparison, one can conclude that TPDL circuits are the best logic family for building the next generation of high density circuits. CGaAs TPDL circuits are also suitable for pipelined architectures. Logic levels are stored on transistor gates of the N-channel transistor logic blocks during the precharging phase. Also, during this phase, the pass gates preceding the logic-blocks are turned off to protect the stored data from corruption.

The effect of changing the supply voltage on the performance of all logic families have been studied. The power supply voltage at which all circuits were simulated are 2.00, 1.75, 1.50, 1.25 and 1.00 volts. The power supply voltage was equal to the peak-to-peak input signal transition. The highest power supply voltage applied to the circuit was limited by the transistor drain-to-source leakage current. The highest gate voltage transition was limited by the transistor gate leakage current. The

maximum operating frequency, as a function of power supply voltage for all logic families, is plotted in Figure 3. The power consumption, as a function of the power supply voltage for all logic families, is plotted in Figure 4. It can be seen from these two figures that the TPDL family has the highest maximum operating frequency with the lowest power consumption. This agrees with the results obtained in the previous sections.

Figure 3: Maximum Operating Frequency of all Logic Families at Different Supply Voltages

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Different dynamic and static logic families implementing four different two-level functions have been designed, simulated and implemented. The performance of TPDL logic is superior to all other dynamic and static logic families. They have the lowest delay-power product ever reported in this technology. TPDL circuits can operate up to 2.38 GHz with a delay-power product of $0.01 \mu\text{W}/\text{MHz}/\text{gate}$. TPDL circuits are suitable for pipelined architecture and are the candidate for the next generation of high speed, high density and low-power CGaAs ICs.

Figure 4: Power Consumption of Logic Families at Different Supply Voltages

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